

Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research and Innovation FIT4RRI

Experiment Summary/Comparative Report (Deliverable 3.5)

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Definitions & Acronym

Big Scholarly Data: Big Data is the Information asset characterised by a High Volume, Velocity and Variety to require specific Technology and Analytical Methods for its transformation into Value.

BSC: Balanced Scorecard

Closed Access: it refers to scientific content which is locked behind a paywall and requires either a subscription or purchase.

Open Access (OA): it refers to online, free of cost access to peer reviewed scientific content with limited copyright and licensing restrictions.

OS: Open Science

R&I: Research and Innovation

RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation

Text and Data Mining (TDM): the process of extracting high quality and meaningful information from text to answer unknown questions.

TOC: Theory of Change

Executive summary

Overview:

This report provides a comparative & summary overview on the 4 co-creation experiments developed within the framework of the FIT4RRI project. As this report presents a high-level overview, it is advisable that reports D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 and D3.4 are consulted prior to browsing through this report. All experiments followed a standardised experiment methodology implementation framework presented in Appendix A of this report as well as were monitoring by using a standardised set of KPIs presented in Appendix B of this report.

Highlights:

- The 4 experiments covered (together) all of the RRI/OS pillars defined in FIT4RRI.
- The internal stakeholders involved in the experiments covered: project managers, heads of units, researchers, directors, managers, PhD students, research support staff, ethics board members and post docs.
- The external stakeholders involved in the experiments covered the entire quadruple helix stakeholder group.
- The quadruple helix co-creation methods contained: focus groups, interviews, workshops, trainings, questionnaires, meetings, brainstorming tools & engagement activities.
- The main blockers to quadruple helix co-creation for RRI & OS embedment are: insufficient solutions, no immediate change of mindset, no proven advantage of RRI, limited involvement of society, money, public perception, lack of awareness, trust, culture, time, communication, lack of quadruple helix co-creation know-how.
- The most relevant outputs from WP1 & WP2 that were tested in the experiments consist of: RRI&OS trends, RRI&OS barriers, thematic & national context analyses, international RRI&OS awareness programmes, RRI&OS networks, RRI&OS-oriented certification processes, multi-actor processes, networking approaches.
- Operational blockers for conducting the experiments: delays in ethics approvals, gathering beneficiaries, political, institutional, social, technical challenges, HR department resistance, general delays, resistance in sharing data, discreditation from employees, lack of higher management commitment, lack of participants, resistance to change & bureaucracy.

Institutional & policy changes:

- RRI&OS diffusion in institutions (awareness raising), introduction of mandatory RRI & OS trainings, introduction of an RRI-based R&D department, RRI&OS embedment in university's third mission strategy, allocation of internal budgets to support further RRI & OS initiatives, external stakeholder education on RRI & OS, development of internal KPIs to measure RRI & OS implementation & adherence, project screening check-list to include RRI & OS items.

Next steps:

- Include more RRI pillars in all experiments, organize more multi-stakeholder workshops, further institutionalize RRI & OS adoption, development of institutional RRI & OS training resources, development of community RRI & OS events, mandatory ethics training courses for postgraduate students & RRI & OS -infused doctoral conferences, secure funding to further support the institutionalization of RRI & OS, ensure uniform internal policy alignment to foster RRI & OS, scaleup (institutionally) the implementation of RRI & OS.

1. Description of the experiments

1.1 The need for the FIT4RRI quadruple-helix co-creation experiments

A FIT4RRI experiment consists of the action of engaging quadruple helix (academia, industry, government, society) stakeholders in an observation of an ongoing research towards identifying ways that quadruple helix co-creation would enable a proper RRI and OS embedment in the ongoing research as well as in the organizations of the participating quadruple helix stakeholders. This may include testing various strategies from WP1 and WP2 as well as presentation of training tools from WP4.

WP3 (Co-creation experiments) was contextualised within the overall interpretation underlying the present situation of RRI and Open Science (OS) and expressed in the project structure.

Science, as any other institution of modernity (political institutions, trade unions, institutional religions, etc.), is suffering from the shift from modern to post-modern society. Quite paradoxically, while science is becoming technically stronger (in terms of impacts and results), it is also becoming socially weaker.

RRI & OS should be therefore placed in this general context.

- In the EC narrative, RRI & OS is an ethically-oriented strategy proposed as a way to improve science-society relations through measures and initiatives aimed at favouring a better alignment of science with societal values, needs and expectations. According to this view, therefore:
 - science is presently under-responsible toward society
 - to increase its responsibility, it is necessary to increase the ethical levels of science and scientists
 - to do that, a prescriptive approach (i.e., including new rules, practices, codes of conduct, etc.) is needed
 - this approach is expected to strengthen the capacity of research institutions to be reflexive, i.e., to better monitoring their own choices and actions and anticipating long-terms consequences of such choices and actions.
- However, this overall approach to RRI & OS – also according to the topic - has not been so successful so far: it is not diffused yet among STEMs; it is a subject of debate only in a strict circle of experts and social scientists; it likely to be perceived from many researchers as “another useless obligation” to be matched since it has not any connection with professional life or personal interests of researchers and with the need of research institutions.
- One of the possible explanations for such disappointing results can be that institutional motivations are not strong enough for raising the interest and mobilisation of researchers, research managers and other stakeholders. On the contrary, for mobilising them, they

should be led to perceive RRI & OS as something useful for managing the problems they meet in their professional life and generated by the processes of change affecting science.

Therefore, FIT4RRI aimed at breaking this barrier and put the related stakeholders in a hands-on co-creation through the 4 quadruple helix co-creation experiments. To this end, the concept of “quadruple helix co-creation” was employed (Figure 1.0).

Figure 1.0 Quadruple Helix Co-creation

The quadruple helix co-creation approach employed in FIT4RRI is based upon an active co-creation among each involved stakeholder. Chesbrough (2013) argued that cocreation is the cornerstone of open innovation practices in today's society, as well as the cornerstone of achieving consensus and true engagement of all stakeholders. More recently, Carayiannis (2015) introduced the concept of targeted open innovation arguing that open innovation should be focused, strategic, and tailored to the current needs of the stakeholders. To achieve this, the FIT4RRI co-creation experiments engaged both internal and external quadruple helix actors into ongoing & new research projects in order to better foster the adoption of RRI&OS.

1.2 Experiment structure & rationale

The experiment objectives that were pursued by the FIT4RRI Experiments are: Testing some of the main outputs emerging from WP1 (on governance settings), WP2 (on sectoral variability with respect to RRI) and WP4 (on training tools and actions). Directly observing the RRI and OS in action, i.e. social, cultural and organisational dynamics activated by the experiments, thus generating direct knowledge on RRI-related processes including, e.g. RRI general trends, barriers to and drivers of RRI, the interests and values involved with RRI, or feasibility and transferability conditions of RRI advanced practices. This work will foster the development of both an RRI Training Improvement and Consolidation Plan (WP4) and the Governance

Settings Support Action (WP5). Each experiment lasted for 16 months and required a highly-intensive synergy and effort (M10-M26).

The driving principles of the experiments can be summarised as follows:

- All experiments concerned both RRI and OS as a whole (i.e. all its components) even though at least two RRI components may be developed more (for example, open access and public engagement, public engagement and education, gender equality and ethics, etc.).
- All experiments were aimed at testing both new training tools or actions and new governance settings, on the basis of outputs from WP1, WP2 and WP4.
- All experiments were subjected to an external observation by the WP leader (SEERC), which was not directly involved with any experiment. Such observation was aimed at 1) comparing the experiments with each other, 2) favouring a mutual learning among the promoters of the experiments and 3) drawing out of the experiments indications for developing the RRI Training Improvement and Consolidation Plan (WP4) and the Governance Settings Support Action (WP5).

The four co-creation experiments included, for each experiment, a designing process phase, including an appraisal of the situation in each involved RFPO, the implementation of the experiments, their evaluation, the organisation of a follow-up workshop involving all the involved players and the drafting of an experiment report. A comparative analysis of the four experiments is carried out in this document.

All experiments were limited in scope and expected outputs and concerned a restricted number of practices concerning specific key pillars of RRI and aspects of OS. They were participatory in nature, involving external and internal stakeholders since the designing phase.

They followed a common structure, including: a) Appraisal of the situation in the involved RFPOs; b) Experiment designing process (to be also carried out through consultation of relevant stakeholders); c) Implementation; d) Organisation of a follow-up workshop involving all the involved players; e) Evaluation; f) Drafting of the experiment reports.

More in detail, the co-creation experiments met the need of:

- testing RRI tools, practices as well as governance settings favouring the embedment of RRI/OS. This testing exercise will mainly concern topics pertaining to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) selected from those related to H2020 societal challenges and industrial leadership pillars.
- engaging with RRI, through the selected pilot sites, actors from Academia, Government, Industry and Citizens (according to Quadruple Helix Model) to favour the uptake of bottom up, inclusive and co-creative actions;

- testing the interaction and coordination among different kinds of knowledge, both of scientific and non-scientific nature, involved with co-creation processes.

Figure 1.1 Experiment Objectives

This choice originates from the assumption that usually STEMs are less porous to RRI and OS. In this framework, under FIT4RRI, an effort will be made to involve the most resilient actors from the beginning. This approach will allow to represent RRI and OS as transversal issues that should be dealt with in all RFPOs. A comprehensive insight into this matter as well as a scientific guideline for tackling the experiment (including the experiment methodology) can be found in the report entitled “Experiment Methodology” – attached in Appendix A.

All experiments followed a standardised experiment methodology attached in Appendix A.

Figure 1.2 Experiment Methodology

The next subsections will briefly introduce the topics of each of the 4 experiments. The topics have been defined in the project's description of action based on a detailed systematic review covering the main application areas of RRI & OS (in terms of existing gaps).

1.3 Experiment 1 – ISQ – Developing an RRI-infused R&D Unit

ISQ (quality assurance company from Portugal) embraced a wider objective of developing an ISQ RRI model & implement it in ISQ R&D unit (as the company was undergoing the process of establishing an R&D unit).

In this sense, the objectives underlying this major experiment were:

- Empower ISQ researchers on RRI.
- Create a Roadmap with recommendations and how to include the society (to include the quadruple helix) for ISQ's R&D activity.
- Develop an RRI model for ISQ and a strategic plan to implement it.

The RRI concept was unknown to ISQ when FIT4RRI project started, so the first challenge to ISQ's project management and implementation team was to understand what lies beneath RRI and Open Science. This constituted what we called a "Learning step". Being involved in WP1 and WP2 development strongly contributed to this and the sectorial workshop organised in Portugal (WP2) allowed a better perception of the whole issue, along with an initial workshop organised in Trondheim, by the time of the second project meeting.

From this whole experiment, ISQ faced a series of achievements:

1. An ISQ RRI model, considering the four pillars we focused on, is under design and will be embedded in the R&D Department mission and strategy; KPI to measure the success of implementation of this model will be set in the overall KPI set for the department annual assessment;
2. ISQ researchers were empowered on RRI during the experiment implementation and there is now an internal guideline to provide RRI training to every new researcher that is recruited to ISQ;
3. An internal repository was created and ISQ is joining an Open Access repository;
4. ISQ is now spreading the word of RRI in the STEM world: an RRI dimension was already included in an approved Sector Skills Alliance (Erasmus+ Programme) project in the Additive Manufacturing sector, as well as in another newly approved Sector Skills Alliance project on Industrial Symbiosis.

A full description of this experiment can be found in D3.1.

1.4 Experiment 2 – University of Liverpool – Photonics & Optical Monitoring

The University of Liverpool experiment focused on an optical monitoring healthcare system that will be placed in the living space of vulnerable people in residential care homes to monitor patterns in behaviour through movement. The main aim of the monitoring system is to help people to stay safe in their living environments and help care workers to deliver quality care through the prevention of falls and ensure that people are active. The system monitors patterns associated in the long-term deterioration in health.

The experiment was carried out in The University of Liverpool (UK) with a mixture of internal (university staff) and external participants. We asked the participants to fill out self-report questionnaires to gain a benchmark of where their level of understanding was on the subjects of ethics and science education (related to the aforementioned topic). They were then invited to take part in a focus group where collectively we discussed how to better embed the RRI principals into research projects. This is where the monitoring system case study was used to give the participants an understanding of the type of research projects we are working on. From this focus group we then conducted one-to-one interviews with each of the participants to reflect on what was discussed at the focus group and how this can be embedded into their current role. Also as part of the interview we asked the participant what they would like to see in the upcoming workshop and what they were hoping to learn from the event. Based on these answers a workshop was constructed for the participants to expand their knowledge and understanding of RRI, focusing on ethics and science education. Each participant was then asked to repeat the questionnaire to measure if there was a development in understanding.

A full description of this experiment can be found in D3.2.

1.5 Experiment 3 – University of Rome “Sapienza” – Material Science

The objective of this experiment was to implement, within an ongoing Sapienza project (Italy) aimed at the creation of a new research center, a responsible governance capable of strengthening the university’s capacity of generating social impact & value (Saperi&Co).

Saperi&Co. (Sapienza enhances research, innovation & co-working) is a project funded by structural funds aimed at implementing a distributed infrastructure based on interdisciplinarity, multi-actor approach and the sharing of competences and knowledge. Saperi&Co. has been developed according to a hub-model putting together several laboratories and a central physical R&I infrastructure hosting:

- a fab-lab
- a coworking spaces

- a training room
- 4 labs based on regional S3.

Saperi&Co. offers a wide range of R&I services and, after the conclusion of the project on April the 30th, the University has established an interdepartmental research centre, including activities on sustainability and biomaterials engineering deriving from the Uniroma1 FIT4RRI group.

A full description of this experiment can be found in D3.3.

1.6 Experiment 4 – Open University – Text & Data Mining

This experiment organized by the Open University (UK) is focused on Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data. The current amendments and exceptions in the Copyright Law have given us the green light to text and data mine (TDM) content we have acquired access to for non-commercial research. eduTDM aims to find a pragmatic solution to arrange how this content can be delivered to text miners as easily as possible based on the subscription they have.

In the past the Open University has investigated the machine accessibility of the Hybrid Gold Open Access publications for text and data mining purposes. The Open University would like to extend this work to non-open access publications; it wishes to investigate and work closely with publishers in order to be able to offer to text miners this massive closed access corpus of publications for text mining purposes. This work will involve initiating a close collaboration with publishers and the creation of a communication route between the Open University and the publishers.

In order to reach to a pragmatic solution and examine whether the stakeholders agree with the eduTDM vision, the Open University created a working group (WG) consisting of commercial closed access publishers, open access publishers, companies performing TDM, organisations creating TDM corpuses, policy makers, text and data miners and industry.

A full description of this experiment can be found in D3.4.

1.7 RRI & OS Pillar adherence

Each experiment had to tackle at least two RRI & OS pillars (as defined in the description of action of FIT4RRI):

- Governance
- Public engagement
- Science education
- Open access
- Open science

- Ethics
- Gender equality

Table 1.1 shows an overview on how these pillars were covered.

Table 1.1 – Experiments & RRI/OS pillars

Selected RRI Pillars	Experiments and Organizers						
	Governance	Public Engagement	Science Education	Open Access	Open Science	Ethics	Gender Equality
Material Science (Sapienza)	X	X	X				
Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	X			X	X	X	
Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)			X			X	
Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)	X	X	X	X	X		X

**The ISQ Experiment did not leverage Gender Equality implicitly, however, through their mandatory RRI training requirement resulted after the experiment implementation (as institutional change), all future ISQ researchers will be impacted on relevant RRI pillars (including gender equality). Additionally, during the WP3 duration, ISQ covered Governance, Science education, Open Access and Open Science. Public engagement will also be covered during the project lifetime, but only after the end of WP3. Ethics and gender equality will be covered only after the project ends.*

2. Internal stakeholders description

Internal stakeholders can be:

- The research team (PDRAs, PhDCs, Academics, RAs, etc)
- Research coordinator / Research office
- Finance team
- RRI committees (or any compatible committee representatives: ethics, gender, open access, open science, public outreach, community engagement, etc)

Due to the different nature of each experiment, the following internal stakeholders presented in Table 2.1 were involved.

Table 2.1 – Internal Stakeholders

Experiment and Organizers	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Internal Stakeholders				
Project Managers	X	X	X	X
Heads of Units				X
Researchers	X	X	X	X
Directors	X			X
Managers				X
PhD Students	X		X	
Research Support Staff	X		X	
Ethics Board Members			X	
Post Docs	X			

3. External stakeholders description

External (quadruple helix) stakeholders can be:

- Other external institutions participating in the ongoing/new research
- Local/regional/national policy bodies
- Other field-compatible research centres, researchers and companies
- Citizens and NGOs
- RFPOs and research funding bodies
- RRI related associations/initiatives/influencers

Due to the different nature of each experiment, the following internal stakeholders presented in Table 3.1 were involved.

Table 3.1 – External Stakeholders

Experiment and Organizers External Stakeholders	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Academia	X	X	X	X
Industry	X	X	X	X
Government	X	X	X	X
Society	X		X	X

4. Experiment implementation methods & tools

The experiment organizers were provided with a choice of tools & methods (Appendix A) for implementing the experiment. AN overview on the chosen approaches is presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 – Implementation methods & tools

Experiment and Organizers Experiment Implementation Tools & Methods	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Focus Groups		X	X	X
Interviews			X	X
Workshops	X		X	X
Trainings	X			X
Questionnaires		X	X	X
Meetings		X		X
Brainstorming	X	X		
Awareness and Engagement Activities	X			

7. Lessons learnt

This section will summarize the main lessons learnt from all the 4 experiments.

7.1 Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation

Table 7.1 – Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation & RRI/OS Implementation

Experiment and Organizers	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Main Blockers				
Insufficient solutions				X
No immediate change of mindset				X
No proven advantage of RRI				X
Limited involvement of society		X		
Money		X	X	
Public Perception			X	
Why is it needed?			X	
Lack of awareness		X	X	
Trust		X	X	
Culture			X	
Time		X	X	
Communication			X	
Quadruple helix co-creation knowledge	X			

7.2 Proposed consensus strategies & co-creation approaches/frameworks

Based on the encountered barriers, each experiment organizer was asked to identify consensus strategies & mitigating actions that would ensure the required quadruple helix co-creation to foster RRI & OS embedment. These strategies can be found in Table 7.2 as well as in D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 and D3.4 (in a more detailed approach).

Table 7.2 – Consensus strategies

Experiment and Organizers	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Co-creation approach that reflects and discusses the RRI model			X	X
Creation of R&D department & with stakeholders			X	X
Theory of change	X			
Balanced Scorecard Framework	X			
Technological drivers for co-creation		X	X	
Need to implement ethics strategies			X	
Application of governmental multi-stakeholder co-creation efforts such as the UK Research Excellence Framework (REF) – Impact			X	
Memorandum of agreement for joint work (IP)			X	

7.3 Most relevant RRI practices (from WP1 and WP2) for the experiment

The experiment objectives that were pursued by the FIT4RRI Experiments included testing some of the main outputs emerging from WP1 (on governance settings), WP2 (on sectoral variability with respect to RRI) and WP4 (on training tools and actions). Directly observing the RRI and OS in action, i.e. social, cultural and organisational dynamics activated by the experiments, thus generating direct knowledge on RRI-related processes including, e.g. RRI general trends, barriers to and drivers of RRI, the interests and values involved with RRI, or

feasibility and transferability conditions of RRI advanced practices. The most important RRI practices (WP1, WP2) leveraged in each experiment are presented in Table 7.3.

Table 7.3 – Most relevant practices (WP1, WP2)

Experiment and Organizers	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
RRI Approaches				
Trends	X			
Barriers	X			
Thematic and national context analysis	X			
Openness		X	X	
International RRI awareness program and RRI training program				X
Participation in RRI-oriented national and international programs				X
Participation of the organization in specialized RRI networks				X
RRI-oriented certification processes				X
Multi-actor process			X	
Networking opportunities			X	

7.4 Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars

The most relevant institutional changes are summarized below (more details can be found in D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4):

- **Sapienza co-creation experiment:** informing the university governing bodies and involving researchers in responsible governance matters and actions, thus making them aware that responsibility and openness (inducing thus change) – far from being the latest administrative processes to comply with – could represent an added value in their research work.
- **Photonics – Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)** – it has been identified that better training across more disciplines is needed within the university. A training course for post graduate research students is being developed with the hopes to be tested in the coming term. The success of this course will ensure that more (ideally all) post graduate research students have an understanding of RRI and can therefore embed it in their research.
- **Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)** – N/A due to the decentralized approach of each research team. Specifically, since Open University works in decentralized teams with a large degree of autonomy, the whole concept of institutional change does not apply in their case.

- **ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)** – The introduction of the R&D department (based on RRI – which is a pioneering action internationally).

7.5 Internal & External policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix

The most relevant policy support/changes are summarized below (more details can be found in D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4 as well as in the deliverable of WP5):

Saperi&Co (Sapienza) – the final aim of the co-creation experiment was to define a simple set of guidelines (about 10 main points) for responsible governance within Saperi&Co. To be effective, the guidelines should be approved by the university governing boards, thus witnessing a political support towards RRI and OS.

Nonetheless some policies to favour this process have already been launched:

- creation of a working group including both research and administrative staff to cope with definitions and indicators concerning third mission;
- launch of an internal call for funding (total budget 200 K euro) for implementing science and society relations.

Photonics – Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool) – during the focus group the participants were asked to suggest what policies would be needed to better embed RRI. In groups the participants noted that policies should have a value based approach, have clear guidelines and be easy to understand. Further suggested what for policies to be meaningful and meet trust expectations of the public, it needs to outline how researchers communicate their research and why and how to achieve this. Also highlighted was that policies should state that ethical approval will cover collaborators, this has been an issues on some project participants have taken part in and they felt this addition would save time.

Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University) – this co-experiment differed from the other FIT4RRI experiments whose goal was to promote RRI practices within an organisation. The OU experiment attempted to investigate the text and data mining of big scholarly data by conducting the experiment in an RRI way. For that matter, the experiment focused on educating the stakeholders and engaging with them. From this experiment it became clear that researchers must have an excellent understanding of the stakeholders related to their research question and they must involve as many quadruple helix actors - government, academia, industry, civil society - in the experiment as possible. In addition, it is important to have a regular and clear communication to prevent stakeholder disengagement.

ISQ RRI Model (ISQ):

- Mandatory RRI training for all new researchers entering ISQ;

- Establishment of key performance indicators to measure the success of ISQ RRI model implementation;
- Project screening check-list including RRI items.

7.6 Any issues/constraints noticed during the experiment implementation (i.e. procedural issues)

Table 7.6 – Operational constraints/issues

Experiment and Organizers	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics - Optical Monitoring (University of Liverpool)	Building ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
Delays in getting ethical approval			X	
Getting beneficiaries for the product			X	
Political barriers	X			
Institutional barriers	X			
Social barriers	X			
Organizational and technical challenges		X		
Resistance in HR department				X
Reluctance in sharing contact details				X
Discreditation from employees				X
Lack of commitment from higher management				X
Lack of participants				X
Postponed actions by people				X
Changes during the project				X
Very bureaucratic process			X	

8. Mutual learning workshops outcomes

SEERC organized 2 mutual learning workshops that were aimed at assisting the experiment organizers to co-align their experiments while also providing them with a learning platform that would enable an easier implementation roadmap for the experiments.

8.1 First mutual learning workshop

Date: 10th November 2017

Time: 14:00 – 18:00

Location: NTNU, Trondheim, Norway

Key items for discussion:

14:00 – 14:30 Case study (example) of implementing the experiment methodology (SEERC)

14:30 – 15:50 Individual presentations by each Experiment Organizer (UNIROMA, LIVERPOOL, ISQ, OPEN UNIVERSITY) covering:

- What is the current RRI institutional framework
- What is the actual research that will be experimented upon & how it is linked with the chosen RRI pillars (at least two)
- What RRI best practices would be relevant for your experiment
- Who are the internal & external stakeholders and how they can be involved
- What issues do you foresee
- Each presentation will be 20 minutes

15:50 – 16:20 Break

16:20 – 17:00 Discussion & peer review (SEERC, K&I, everyone)

17:00 – 18:00 Open discussion & QA (everyone)

Summary:

Item 0: Converged starting points

- A FIT4RRI experiment consists of bridging the quadruple helix stakeholders for initiating discussions and investigation/analysis of how WP1, WP2 and WP4 items can be properly implemented within the institutional frameworks of the experiment organizers as well as the required institutional changes at the entire quadruple helix stakeholder group.
- An experiment needs to be performed on an ongoing research (for a specific timeline, without implying that the FIT4RRI experiment should overlap with the start and end dates of the ongoing research).
- The experimentation and change management level is flexible for each experiment organizer as the outcomes of the experiment can range from recommendations for institutional framework (or quadruple helix framework) changes to actual changes implemented in the ongoing research.
- The output of the experiments will be measured by the proposed & implemented changes (institutional, policy, content-wise, etc).

Item 1: The methodology provided by SEERC

- Serves as a procedural guidance document
- Requires content from WP1 and WP2
- Will be updated to reflect the latest requirements

Item 2: Each experiment organizer:

- Should liaise with WP1 and WP2 in order to “retrieve” research questions and relevant content that can be experimented upon in WP3
- Should liaise with WP4 in order to request training tools (specialized) for each experiment that can be used during the experiments (either actual usage or just for awareness raising and information purposes for all the stakeholders)
- Should aim at integrating the areas mentioned in WP1/WP2 in parallel with the chosen RRI/OS pillars

- Should think of ideas for approaching RRI in such a way that it would solve their existing institutional problems (prior to the design of the experiment) – providing thus greater incentives for receiving institutional support & commitment.

Item 3: SEERC will:

- Update the WP3 Experiment Methodology to incorporate the areas discussed in WP1/WP2 and not only the RRI & OS pillars
- Liaise with each experiment organizer to collect the required items from WP1, WP2 and WP4 to be properly included/reported in the WP3 Experiment Methodology
- Propose several storylines/pitches that can be used to attract the quadruple helix stakeholders to the experiments (i.e. co-development of innovative business models, ensuring financial sustainability through RRI, etc). Each partner will adapt the storylines for the context of each experiment.
- Issue a table for each experiment organizer to fill-in (Stakeholder appraisal phase)
- Organize one individual follow-up meeting with each experiment organizer and one group meeting with all experiments by 20th December 2017.
- Investigate the potential of including a methodology/tool for measuring RRI institutionalization as an output of the experiments (change measurement based on qualitative and quantitative metrics).

8.2 Second mutual learning workshop

Date: 1st October 2019

Time: 09:00 – 11:00

Location: SEERC, Thessaloniki, Greece

Key items for discussion:

- Comparative report presentation (SEERC)
- Presentation of summary reports from each experiment (UNIROMA, UNILIV, OU, ISQ)
- External feedback from experts from each experiment

Summary:

- External experts were involved in providing feedback for the experiments (each experiment was paired with an external RRI/OS expert that has received the corresponding experiment report and had the chance to review the work).
- Good levels of experiment implementation satisfaction & achievement were reached.
- The barriers/constraints as well as best practices were discussed and agreed upon.
- The most important barrier (lack of awareness & co-creation/participation of all actors) was raised as key point and it will also be lined with the overall approach for the final FIT4RRI conference in which participatory approaches will be sought.

9. Next steps

The next steps are linked with each institution's (experiment organizer) interest to embed RRI&OS into their internal frameworks. The following next steps for each experiment are summarized below.

ISQ

- **Including more RRI pillars:** Due to the growing interest on the subject and need for the successful implementation of an ISQ RRI model, we will continue the implementation of training actions on the RRI pillars that were not fully approached during WP3 development. Pillars that are still missing training sessions and that the implementation team sees as important to promote are, first of all, the Public Engagement RRI pillar training action, as it is one of the pillars that are considered in the model that is being designed.
- **More workshops:** It is also foreseen the implementation of workshops dedicated to Gender Equality and Ethics pillars, either making use of the training tools available in FOSTER platform or developing our own training tools, but these pillars are out of the scope of the ISQ RRI model that we are developing.
- **Full institutionalization of the ISQ RRI model:** Our RRI model will also be finalised, and an implementation strategy is to be proposed to ISQ board. Meanwhile, a set of KPI related to the implementation of the RRI model will be set and included in the set of indicators defined to measure the new R&D department's performance.
- **RRI check-list for projects:** A project screening procedure will be built for project ideas and a check-list related to our RRI model will be included.
- **Development of institutional RRI/OS training resources:** There will be a specific area in ISQ's institutional website dedicated to our R&D department and gender balance in ISQ researchers will be reported there.

University of Liverpool

- **Community & Open research events:** continue the organization of community events to promote RRI & OS (public engagement).
- **Ethics training courses for PGR students:** all PGR students will receive mandatory ethics training courses (derived from this experiment).

- **RRI & OS training:** PhD conference trainings will be organized to ensure RRI&OS diffusion in the research community (even outside the universities boundaries).
- **Publications:** Articles on the research conducted will be published to support the institutional efforts towards Research Excellence Framework impact cases.
- **Funding:** Funding will be gathered to sustain the FIT4RRI efforts.

Open University

- **Enlarge stakeholder engagement:** With regards to the next steps it is important to specify what is needed from all the stakeholders in order to progress with the eduTDM plan, i.e. funding estimation, time allocation, development resources, discuss security issues.
- **Policy analysis & integration:** In addition, an overview of the governance, and more specifically the roles, responsibilities and considerations for this effort need to be defined. As this is a project that takes advantage of the UK Copyright exception, it will be initially tested in the UK context, but a further exploration in another country/use case could be tested in the future.

UNIROMA

- **Institutional guidelines approval:** The next main goal will be the set up and approval of guidelines for responsible governance within Saperi&Co. The guidelines will be assessed by the expert stakeholders' group that already worked in the participatory design phase.
- **Scaleup responsible governance (institutionally):** Once the guidelines will be approved, they could represent a relevant base to scale up responsible governance to Sapienza and/or other university research centre.
- **Engagement & science education activities:** Another future goal is to organize within Saperi&Co. engagement and science education activities on a more regular base, involving not only civil society but also the other quadruple helix actors.
- **Integrate the experiment with other ongoing projects:** Furthermore, there is the will to connect the experiment with other ongoing initiatives such as CIVIS project funded under the Erasmus European Universities call. In fact, CIVIS foresees that Sapienza will organize a set of open labs for involving and engaging stakeholders in research issues.

Conclusion

This report provided a comparative & summary overview on the 4 co-creation experiments developed within the framework of the FIT4RRI project. All experiments followed a standardised experiment methodology implementation framework (quadruple helix co-creation) presented in Appendix A of this report as well as were monitoring by using a standardised set of KPIs presented in Appendix B of this report. The main blockers to quadruple helix co-creation for RRI & OS embedment have been identified such as: insufficient solutions, no immediate change of mindset, no proven advantage of RRI, limited involvement of society, money, public perception, lack of awareness, trust, culture, time, communication, lack of quadruple helix co-creation know-how. The operational blockers for conducting the experiments: delays in ethics approvals, gathering beneficiaries, political, institutional, social, technical challenges, HR department resistance, general delays, resistance in sharing data, discreditation from employees, lack of higher management commitment, lack of participants, resistance to change & bureaucracy. Nevertheless, the co-creation experiments have brought substantial benefits within the participating institutions: RRI&OS diffusion in institutions (awareness raising), introduction of mandatory RRI & OS trainings, introduction of an RRI-based R&D department, RRI&OS embedment in university's third mission strategy, allocation of internal budgets to support further RRI & OS initiatives, external stakeholder education on RRI & OS, development of internal KPIs to measure RRI & OS implementation & adherence, project screening check-list to include RRI & OS items.

The proposed next steps consist of: inclusion of more RRI pillars in all experiments, organization of more multi-stakeholder workshops, further institutionalize RRI & OS adoption, development of institutional RRI & OS training resources, development of community RRI & OS events, mandatory ethics training courses for postgraduate students & RRI & OS -infused doctoral conferences, secure funding to further support the institutionalization of RRI & OS, ensure uniform internal policy alignment to foster RRI & OS, scaleup (institutionally) the implementation of RRI & OS. All these recommendations have a cross-cutting requirement: foster better quadruple helix co-creation (skills & know-how required for this co-creation).

Appendix A – Experiment Organization Methodology

FIT4RRI
WP3. Co-creation experiments

Experiment Organization Methodology

January 25, 2018

Lead partner: SEERC

Authors: Adrian Solomon (SEERC), Nikos Zaharis (SEERC), Luciano D'Andrea (K&I),
Emanuela Todeva (THA),

1. Introduction

WP3 takes place between Month 8 (December 2017) and Month 28 (August 2019) of the FIT4RRI project. The 4 experiments (tasks 3.1 to 3.4) will have to take place between Month 10 (February 2018) and Month 26 (June 2019). They should allow for “... *Testing some of the main outputs emerging from WP1 (on governance settings), WP2 (on sectoral variability with respect to RRI) and WP4 (on training tools and actions)...*”.

In order to better support the organization of the experiments, the first mutual learning session among the promoters of the experiments was decided to take place together with the next project meeting (scheduled for November 9-10, 2017 in Trondheim, Norway)

Relevant points to be taken under consideration:

- The project is a CSA, so it does not include actual research being performed. The experiments will have to be based on on-going or new research that will take place (either internally or externally funded) in the institutions that promote the experiments and their research and innovation ecosystem.
- Although each one of the experiments will put emphasis on 2-3 RRI and OS components, we should try to diversify as much as possible (trying not to end with emphasis on the same 2-3 components in all experiments and trying to cover as many of them as possible)
- University of Liverpool might want to change slightly the focus of the experiment from Photonics to Sensor networks, which will able them to involve the Sensor City (<http://www.sensorcity.co.uk/>). The PO advised us that it would be OK as long as the field selected is within the partners’ research interests/ agenda and can provide a good basis for the experiment.

Indicative timetable of WP3

Time	Activity
M7 (Nov 2017)	1 st Mutual learning workshop in Trondheim. First phase of “Appraisal of the current situation”; peer observation. Discussion on the draft methodology
M8-M9 (Dec 2017 – Jan 2018)	Finalization of the “external observation and mutual learning methodology”
M10 – M12 (Jan – Mar 2018)	Second phase of “Appraisal of the current situation” and “Design”
M13 – M22 (Apr 2018 – Jan 2019)	Implementation (including 2 on-site visits)
M23-24 (Feb – Mar 2019)	Follow up
M25 (Apr 2019)	2nd Mutual learning workshop
M25 -26 (Apr – May 2019)	Evaluation
M27-28 (June – July 2019)	Reporting

2. Formal description of the experiments

The experiment objectives that will be pursued are: Testing some of the main outputs emerging from WP1 (on governance settings), WP2 (on sectoral variability with respect to RRI) and WP4 (on training tools and actions). Directly observing the RRI and OS in action, i.e. social, cultural and organisational dynamics activated by the experiments, thus generating direct knowledge on RRI-related processes including, e.g. RRI general trends, barriers to and drivers of RRI, the interests and values involved with RRI, or feasibility and transferability conditions of RRI advanced practices. The outputs of this WP will foster the development of both an RRI Training Improvement and Consolidation Plan (WP4) and the Governance Settings Support Action (WP5).

The driving principles of the experiments can be summarised as follows:

- All experiments should concern RRI and OS as a whole (i.e. all its components) even though **at least two RRI components may be developed more** (for example, open access and public engagement, public engagement and education, gender equality and ethics, etc.).
- All experiments should be aimed at testing both new training tools or actions and new governance settings, on the basis of outputs from WP1, WP2 and WP4.
- All experiments should be the subject of an external observation by the WP leader (SEERC), which will be not directly involved with any experiment. Such observation will be aimed at 1) comparing the experiments with each other, 2) favouring a mutual learning among the promoters of the experiments and 3) drawing out of the experiments indications for developing the RRI Training Improvement and Consolidation Plan (WP4) and the Governance Settings Support Action (WP5).

The four co-creation experiments will include, for each experiment, a designing process phase, including an appraisal of the situation in each involved RFPO, the implementation of the experiments, their evaluation, the organisation of a follow-up workshop involving all the involved players and the drafting of an experiment report. A comparative analysis of the four experiments will be also carried out.

All experiments will be limited in scope and expected outputs and will concern a restricted number of practices concerning specific key pillars of RRI and aspects of OS. They will be participatory in nature, involving external and internal stakeholders since the designing phase. They will all follow a common structure, including: a) Appraisal of the situation in the involved RFPOs; b) Experiment designing process (to be also carried out through consultation of relevant stakeholders); c) Implementation; d) Organisation of a follow-up workshop involving all the involved players; e) Evaluation; f) Drafting of the experiment reports.

More in detail, the co-creation experiments will meet the need of:

- testing RRI tools, practices as well as governance settings favouring the embedment of RRI/OS. This testing exercise will mainly concern topics pertaining to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) selected from those related to H2020 societal challenges and industrial leadership pillars

- engaging with RRI, through the selected pilot sites, actors from Academia, Government, Industry and Citizens (according to Quadruple Helix Model) to favour the uptake of bottom up, inclusive and co-creative actions;
- testing the interaction and coordination among different kinds of knowledge, both of scientific and non-scientific nature, involved with co-creation processes.

This choice originates from the assumption that usually STEMs are less porous to RRI and OS. In this framework, under FIT4RRI, an effort will be made to involve the most resilient actors from the beginning. This approach will allow to represent RRI and OS as transversal issues that should be dealt with in all RFPOs. A comprehensive insight into this matter as well as a scientific guideline for tackling the experiment can be found in Appendix A-G.

3. Contextual positioning of the Experiments

General context

WP3 should be contextualised within the overall interpretation underlying the present situation of RRI and Open Science (OS) and expressed in the project structure.

- Science, as any other institution of modernity (political institutions, trade unions, institutional religions, etc.), is suffering from the **shift from modern to post-modern society**. Quite paradoxically, while science is becoming technically stronger (in terms of impacts and results), it is also becoming socially weaker.
- Some **critical issues** pertaining to science are, for example:
 - decreasing authoritativeness and social recognition of scientific institutions and, to a certain extent, decreasing credibility of scientists
 - growing diffusion (as an effect of the emergence of the so-called “post-factual age”) of societal views (of facts, events, processes) which are explicitly alternative or even opposite to those based on science, often propelled by anti-science attitudes and pseudo-scientific beliefs

- ever-stronger connection between science and ethical and policy issues, triggering and feeding social tensions on controversial issues and “public battle” among experts
 - increasing sensitiveness of the public towards science-related risks
 - people’s decreasing trust in scientific institutions leading to a growing demand for accountability and transparency
 - need for science institutions to increasingly demonstrate their social and economic usefulness to citizens as taxpayers.
- It is easy to see that these critical issues are similar to those affecting the other social institutions of modernity. See for example some of the phenomena affecting **politics**:
- decreasing authoritativeness, social recognition and credibility of politicians and political parties
 - growing diffusion of anti-political and populist views, leading to a decreasing people’s propensity to vote
 - ever-stronger connection between politics and ethical issues, especially regarding aspects like migration policies, privacy, security, medical issues, or civil rights
 - increasing sensitiveness of the public towards risks connected to politics (for example, corruption, connections between politics and industry, high costs of political institutions, etc.)
 - people’s decreasing trust in politicians and political institutions leading to a growing demand for accountability and transparency
 - need for politicians and political institutions to increasingly demonstrate their capacity and usefulness to citizens as taxpayers.
 -
- The real difference is that, while the crisis of politics is evident (in Europe as well as in USA at least), the crisis of science is not perceived as such.
- Reacting to the shift from modernity to post-modernity, science is now experiencing a long, complex and sometimes painful **transitional process of change** which has been interpreted through different models (such as the Model-Mode2 model¹, the Post-academic science², or the Post-Normal science³), which tried to account for the many transformations affecting scientific institutions, including, e.g., increase in the political steering, competitive access to research funds, increase in the physical mobility of researchers, decrease in the availability of tenure positions (while the number of young researchers constantly increases) with the effect of a growing labour instability, increase in the administrative obligations, growing tendency to evaluate research process in terms of technological innovations, etc.
- Therefore, changes in **science-society relations** are only one of the many changes characterising this transitional process, even though all these changes are strongly connected with each other.

RRI

RRI should be therefore placed in this general context.

¹ Nowotny, H., Scott, P., Gibbons, M. (2001) *Re-thinking Science: Knowledge and the Public in the Age of Uncertainty*, Cambridge: Polity Press; Nowotny, H., Scott, P., Gibbons, M. (2003) ‘Mode 2 Revisited’: *The New Production of Knowledge. Minerva*, 41

² Ziman, J. (2000) *Real Science. What it is, and what it means*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

³ Funtowicz S.O., Ravetz R.J. (1993) Science for the post-normal age, *Futures*, September

- In the EC narrative, RRI is an **ethically-oriented strategy** proposed as a way to improve science-society relations through measures and initiatives aimed at favouring a better alignment of science with societal values, needs and expectations. According to this view, therefore:
 - science is presently under-responsible toward society
 - to increase its responsibility, it is necessary to increase the ethical levels of science and scientists
 - to do that, a prescriptive approach (i.e., including new rules, practices, codes of conduct, etc.) is needed
 - this approach is expected to strengthen the capacity of research institutions to be reflexive, i.e., to better monitoring their own choices and actions and anticipating long-terms consequences of such choices and actions.

- However, this overall approach to RRI – also according to the Topic - **has not been so successful** so far: it is not diffused yet among STEMs; it is a subject of debate only in a strict circle of experts and social scientists; it likely to be perceived from many researchers as “another useless obligation” to be matched since it has not any connection with professional life or personal interests of researchers and with the need of research institutions.

- One of the possible explanations for such disappointing results can be that **ethical motivations** are not strong enough for raising the interest and mobilisation of researchers, research managers and other stakeholders. On the contrary, for mobilising them, they should be led to **perceive RRI as something useful** for managing the problems they meet in their professional life and generated by the processes of change affecting science.

4. Experiment organization methodology

The aforementioned points may suggest something about **nature, organisation and development** of the experiments.

- As for the **nature** of the experiments, they should be viewed as an attempt to apply RRI in the daily life of the concerned institutions as an approach helping them address the critical issues they are already involved with. This means not to necessarily developing a new brand project/programme on which RRI should be applied, but developing an RRI programme which may be applied in different research programmes or in managing different aspects of the life of the concerned institutions, departments or research groups.

- As for the **organisation** of the experiments, we are aware of how it could be difficult for STEM scientists to cope with aspects of the life of their organisations which are not apparently directly connected with the core of their research activities. However, it is not a fruitful strategy to hire an external expert on RRI in charge of making the experimentation, while researchers keep on doing their activities as usual. Rather, it is necessary that researchers and managers of the organisation should be primarily concerned with the experimentations since they only know if and how RRI can be useful for their professional life or for their institution. Afterwards, they may also decide to hire someone else, but they should be on the forefront of the experimentation all along the project duration.

The Proposed RRI Experiment Multiplex Methodology Structure:

4.1 Ongoing Stage: Mutual learning

Learning step

- The teams in charge of the experimentations can access key inputs on RRI (ideas, definitions, cases already developed, etc.) so as to allow them better understanding what is at stake with RRI as well as what are the gaps and main best practices.

Analytical step

- Each team was asked (already) to map the main problems and critical issues they are worry about or they have to address in their professional activities; a Skype call was organized on the 17th of July 2017 and each experiment organizer was asked to list all the relations they have with external actors for any reason connected with their core activities (for example, contacts with funding agencies, industries, media, publishers, high schools, science parks, local authorities, service providers, etc.), since RRI mainly concerns science-society relations; another exercise could be that of analysing the life of the organisation/department/research group through the lens of the six RRI keys (open access, gender, public engagement, education, ethical issues, governance) and Open Science (innovation processes, cooperation with the many actors involved with innovation, etc.)

4.2 Stage 1: RFPO Appraisal & Design (MAP)

4.2.1 Reflexive step

The first main step in the implementation of the experiments is the identification of the actual (ongoing/new) research that will be observed (experimented upon) and description of its main features as exemplified in the table 4.2.1 below:

Table 4.2.1 Step 1.1 Experiment context & RRI Pillars

Organizer	<name of the institution>
Title	<title of the research in progress>
Description	<maximum 250 words denoting aims/objectives/expected outcomes / methodology >
Stakeholders	<list which actors internal & external are involved>
RRI Pillars	<justify for each RRI pillar how the research is tangent>
Selected RRI pillars	<justify in details why the selected (2) RRI pillars are the most relevant ones: max 250 words>

4.2.2 Mapping & consultation step

The next step is the stakeholder mapping process (identify internal + external stakeholders).

Table 4.2.2 Step 1.2 Stakeholder mapping

<p>List the internal stakeholders</p>	<p>Internal stakeholders can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research team (PDRAs, PhDCs, Academics, RAs, etc) • Research coordinator / Research office • Finance team • RRI committees (or any compatible committee representatives: ethics, gender, open access, open science, public outreach, community engagement, etc) <p>Provide a list with names, full titles/positions and contact of all the aforementioned stakeholders.</p>
<p>List the external stakeholders</p>	<p>External (quadruple helix) stakeholders can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other external institutions participating in the ongoing/new research • Local/regional/national policy bodies • Other field-compatible research centres, researchers and companies • Citizens and NGOs • RFPOs and research funding bodies • RRI related associations/initiatives/influencers <p>How to identify the external stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertaking a sectoral profile in the region/country to identify the key external players in this field • Undertaking a sectoral profile in other successful regions/countries from EU where the stakeholder-group is well-established in order to identify new relevant external stakeholders • Identification of the main regulatory framework that governs the experiment's sector in order to reach the responsible institution (that monitors/control the regulation) • Identification of the financing sources of the specific research & RFPO involved in financing the research • Analysis of the regional/national innovation & science communication policy framework in order to understand the actors involved • Analysis of similar research performed by fellow (or top performing) institutions in order to identify the names of the innovators in this field

	Provide a list with names, full titles/positions and contact of all the identified stakeholders.
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After the stakeholders are mapped (identified), a consultation step will follow:

Table 4.2.2 Step 1.3 Stakeholder consultation

Survey/Interview	<p>A survey (2 responses per stakeholder type) targeting both internal & external stakeholders will be implemented. The survey will contain the following items:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the ongoing/new research • Description of RRI principles • Description of the purpose of the experiment • Assessment of the know-how/implementation of RRI (or individual pillar) in the stakeholders' institution/work • Assessment of the stakeholder's institutional RRI (or individual pillar) governance settings • Assessment of the stakeholder's interest, motivation, perceived usefulness of RRI (or individual pillar) • Assessment of the relevance/usefulness of key related RRI practices & governance settings emerged from WP1, WP2, WP3 • Qualitative input related to the experiment implementation (how to bring the quadruple helix (related to the ongoing/new research) together more effectively for the purpose of embedding RRI in their institutional frameworks. • Assessment of the stakeholder's interest in participating in the focus group, follow-up interview and follow-up workshop related to the envisioned experiment <p>A full data collection tool (questionnaire) is provided in Appendix A-A.</p>
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4.2.3 Designing step

The experiment design step consists of the blueprint required to engage quadruple helix stakeholders in an observation of an ongoing research towards identifying ways that quadruple helix co-creation would enable a proper RRI embedment in the ongoing research as well as in the organizations of the participating quadruple helix stakeholders. In order to proceed to this stage, the stakeholder mapping and consultation must have been finalized to ensure that the entire stakeholder group and their views are properly considered in the experiment design process. As a guide for the design phase, the following table provides an overview:

Table 4.2.3 Step 2.1 Experiment design

Organizer	<name>
Topic	<topic.. i.e. photonics energy data mining material science >

Selected RRI Pillars	<list the most relevant pillars>
Objectives	<p>Stipulate the RRI-OS objectives of the experiment (based on the topic and of the research project's as well as stakeholders' needs that were identified through the consultation step)</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify how to embed gender equality in data mining research with the support of the quadruple helix stakeholders • Assess what changes are required in the research design in order to embed gender equality and how would each stakeholder support/impact on this • What organizational changes are required for each stakeholder in order to foster this embedment at the stakeholder group • Refer to any institutional framework affecting the relevant RRI/OS pillars i.e. ethics internal policies; gender equality internal policies; public engagement strategies etc <p>The objectives will include also the debate on best practices and governance policies from WP1, WP2 and will impact on WP5.</p>
Focus group	<p>Organize a first focus group with internal + external stakeholders in order to discuss the objectives of the experiment (and the experiment overall). This implies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set the date & time of the focus group (2.5h) • Send invitation to the identified stakeholders to participate in the focus group • Implement the focus group with the objectives that have been set. <p>The goal of this focus group would be to open to the debate for the achievement/implementation of the previously set objectives. As a result, a clear set of actions will emerge. After this focus group, each stakeholder will be asked to “resume” their normal operation in their institutions and assess/identify how the objectives (through the emerged set of actions) can be implemented (in theory) and what changes/further actions would be required. Such changes can be operational, regulatory, etc. In any case, the idea is to minimize the effort for the stakeholders in order to ensure they participation.</p>
Focus group implementation approach	<p>The multi-stakeholder management during the focus groups will be implemented following the guideline(s) from Appendix A-B. Of course, each experiment organizer is encouraged to adapt the guidelines based on the local needs & specific stakeholder requirements.</p>

<p>Follow-up interview/questionnaire</p>	<p>Organize a follow-up interview/questionnaire with (the same) internal + external stakeholders in order to discuss the follow-up on the actions set in the first focus group.</p> <p>The objective would be to understand to what extent the previously set actions can be implemented and if (perhaps) any other blockers are emerging while also updating on the research progress. This would enable the internal stakeholders to incorporate progress-feedback in their process of assessing the implementation of the highest rated/debated RRI best practices to support the implementation of the chosen RRI pillars.</p> <p>The interview/questionnaire guide can be found in Appendix A-C.</p>
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4.3 Stage 2: Experiment implementation (ENGAGE)

4.3.1 Implementation step

The experiments will be implemented based on the previously developed design. Throughout the implementation, inter-experiment team exchanges (within FIT4RRI) as well as experiment observation will take place.

4.3.2 Exchange step

During the implementation of the experiments, the teams will promote an idea exchange among them so as to building a common view of the experimentations and to learn from each-other. The information exchange will be done by relying on the template from [Appendix A-D](#).

4.4 Stage 3: Experiment observation (MEASURE)

The ultimate role of observation is not to act as a corrective measure but to identify learning opportunities that will be discussed in the follow-up workshops. The observation will take place three times for each experiment at the following stages:

- Initial stage (after the experiment design is finalized)
- Mid-stage (after the follow-up interviews)
- Final stage (after the follow-up workshop)

The observation will be based on the KPIs defined in [Appendix A-E](#).

4.5 Stage 4: Follow-up workshop

The aim of the follow-up workshop is to be as a wrapper learning exercise (and includes the internal & external stakeholders involved in the experiments). Here we need to reflect on the entire process - what was good, what went wrong and how we can leverage this learning exercise to an upper level while also amending/improving the methodology. All this needs to be done in co-creation with all stakeholders. The follow-up workshop should take place within 3 months from the follow-up interviews (6 months after the experiment started). The idea is to minimize the time span in order to keep the stakeholders interested and to mitigate the risk of having the stakeholders change jobs, etc.

Table 4.5.1 Step 4.1 Follow-up workshop

Organizer	<name>
Topic	<topic.. i.e. photonics energy data mining material science >
Selected RRI Pillars	<list the most relevant pillars>
Objectives	<p>Stipulate the objectives of the follow-up workshop to be tailored around the following questions that can be asked during the workshop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the research progress over the past 6 months and how the quadruple helix co-creation towards RRI embedment triggered changes / issues / clashes • Reflect on what was agreed upon by each quadruple helix stakeholders in terms of the necessary co-creation • Reflect on the necessary institutional changes required by each stakeholder in order to properly embed RRI • Reflect on how each stakeholder can act as an ambassador of RRI in its institution to support long-term sustainable change • Assess which practices from WP1 and WP2 are the most relevant ones (from the ones that have been included in the experiments) • Assess which governance settings need updates or different framework to support the work of WP5 • Devise a memorandum of understanding/agreement to keep the stakeholders connected <p>Lastly, Items 5, 6, 7 and 8 from Appendix A will be re-tested during the workshop in order to measure any changes within the quadruple helix' stakeholders' perception of RRI after they have been engaged throughout the experiment implementation.</p>

4.6 Final stage: Comparative analysis report

- Here we provide a comparative report of the 4 experiments with a concrete break-down on their objectives, stages, outcomes, learning exercises, etc. + impact on WP1, 2, 5. A detailed reporting template will be provided in order for each experiment to have a standardized reporting framework. An indicative structure of such template is provided in [Appendix A-F](#).

Appendix A-A – Stakeholder consultation tool

Item 1

Welcome note & introduction to the survey

Item 2

Description of RRI (i.e. by taking the approach of WP2 with the sectoral workshops – better focusing on the RRI pillars rather than mentioning RRI per se)

Item 3

Description of the ongoing research subjected to the experimentation

Item 4

Description of the aim of this experiment

Item 5

5.1 To what extent are you aware of [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly aware]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

5.2 To what extent are you aware of your institution implementing [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly aware]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

5.2 To what extent are you aware of your institution having internal policies for [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly aware]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

Item 6

6.1 How motivated are you to implement [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly motivated]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

6.2 How motivated is your institution to implement [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly motivated]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

6.3 How useful do you believe it is to implement [RRI Pillar X – one question for each pillar, 1-Not at all, 5 – Highly useful]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

Item 7

7.1 Please rate the following practices and governance settings based on your perceived importance for your institution and research [Practice X, Governance Setting X (emerged from WP1, WP2, WP3) – one question for each item, 1-Not at all important, 5 – Highly important]

1 2 3 4 5

Comments:

Item 8

8.1 To what extent do you involve the following stakeholders in your research design, implementation and follow-up ? [1 – Not at all; 5 – A lot]

1 2 3 4 5

Other researchers

Industry

Society

Policy makers

8.2 What are the main blockers that prohibit you to engage the entire quadruple helix (all four actors) ?

Comment:

8.3 Are you aware who are the relevant quadruple helix stakeholders from your research-related ecosystem ?

Comment:

8.4 What would you need in order to properly bring together the quadruple helix stakeholders?

Comment:

8.5 How would you envision the quadruple helix co-creation for better embedding [RRI Pillar X] in the context of the aforementioned research (from Item 3)

Comment:

Item 9

Are you interested in taking part in our experiment involving 1 focus group, 1 follow-up interview and 1 workshop over the next 6 months?

Yes No

Appendix A-B – Focus group implementation guide

Participants: internal + external stakeholders

Duration: 2.5 hours

Objectives related to embedding RRI in the ongoing research (as described in Table 4.2.3):

- OBJx
- ...

Suggested items & questions to be asked:

- Introductions & overview on the research, chosen RRI pillars, objectives and focus group.
- For each stakeholder: current awareness & implementation of the item related to OBJx [repeat for each objective]
- For the internal stakeholders: what do you require from industry and policy in order to better embed the chosen RRI pillars into your ongoing research?
- For the internal stakeholders: how can you better involve society in your research design, implementation & follow-up stages and how would this impact on embedding the chosen RRI pillars in your research ?
- For industry & RFPOs: what would make you engage more with researchers/universities (i.e. internal stakeholders) in order to properly facilitate the embedment of RRI in the ongoing research? What perceived benefits do you foresee and what are the blockers? How is the policy framework supporting such engagement?
- For policy makers: How should the co-creation between the internal stakeholders, society and industry evolve in order to properly contribute to the national/regional policies on the chosen RRI pillars? What are your main mechanisms to control and monitor the developments of RRI pillars implementation (and how do you measure the impact at a local/regional/national level)?
- For industry, RFPOs & policy: Would you be willing to provide funding for boosting the embedment of the chosen RRI pillars for the ongoing research? If yes, then under what circumstances (here you can mention examples of practices from WP1 and WP2 and ask which ones are the most relevant)?
- For society: How would you expect to be involved and contribute in the design, implementation and follow-up stages of this ongoing research? How will your contribution impact on embedding the chosen RRI pillars?

- Consensus: Direct the discussions towards achieving (if possible) a consensus among the stakeholders and set the following next steps that each stakeholder will have to think about over the next 3 months:
 - Internal stakeholders (as well as external researchers/universities): Identify how to involve the quadruple helix stakeholders for better boosting the embedment of the chosen RRI pillars in the ongoing research. A practical approach could be adopted by the internal stakeholders by assessing how the most relevant RRI practices (WP1, WP2) that have been debated during the focus group could be implemented in practical terms.
 - Policy makers: identify what policy changes are required (and if they are feasible) to better support the quadruple helix co-creation.
 - Industry & RFPOs: identify potential cooperation opportunities with the internal stakeholders and what would be the framework/expected outcomes (win-win) in terms of enhancing the embedment of the chosen RRI pillars.
 - Society: identify the current/ongoing needs (based on the overall context discussed in the focus group & related to the chosen RRI pillars) and access to science requirements and propose ways for the internal stakeholders to account them in the research stages.

Appendix A-C – Follow-up interview guide

The objective of the follow-up interview is to understand to what extent the previously set actions can be implemented and if (perhaps) any other blockers are emerging while also updating on the research progress.

The targets upon which the progress should be reported are:

- Internal stakeholders (as well as external researchers/universities): Identify how to involve the quadruple helix stakeholders for better boosting the embedment of the chosen RRI pillars in the ongoing research. A practical approach could be adopted by the internal stakeholders by piloting the most relevant RRI practices (WP1, WP2) that have been debated during the focus group.
- Policy makers: identify what policy changes are required (and if they are feasible) to better support the quadruple helix co-creation.
- Industry & RFPOs: identify potential cooperation opportunities with the internal stakeholders and what would be the framework/expected outcomes (win-win) in terms of enhancing the embedment of the chosen RRI pillars.
- Society: identify the current/ongoing needs (based on the overall context discussed in the focus group & related to the chosen RRI pillars) and access to science requirements and propose ways for the internal stakeholders to account them in the research stages.

Each stakeholder will be contacted by phone for a brief interview (30 minutes) in order to follow-up for each of the set targets. The aim of this follow-up is for the internal stakeholders to incorporate

progress-feedback in their process of piloting (or assessing the implementation of) the chosen RRI best practices.

Appendix A-D – Inter-experiment information exchange

In order for the experimentation teams to inform each-other, Google files containing the following information will be created (by SEERC) and updated by each experiment organizer as soon as the information becomes available (on an ongoing basis throughout the entire lifecycle of the experiment).

Experiment organizer	
Experiment topic	
Chosen RRI pillars	
Highest rated RRI best practice(s)	
Quadruple helix co-creation barriers and solutions	
Awareness & implementation levels for each RRI pillar by each stakeholder	
Internal stakeholder requirements to better embed RRI in the ongoing research	
Industry/RFPOs requirements and collaboration framework with researchers	
Policy support, control & monitoring mechanisms for RRI pillar embedment	
Societal contribution to RRI infused research and societal requirements	
Observed/reported organizational change requirements to better foster RRI embedment	
Experience & pitfalls from the focus-group implementation and on-spot discussion	
Experience & pitfalls from the follow-up interview implementation	
Experience & pitfalls from the workshop implementation and on-spot discussion	
Progress reporting on the assessment of potentially implementing the highest rated RRI practices in the ongoing research	

Appendix A-E – Key performance indicators

The ultimate role of observation is not to act as a corrective measure but to identify learning opportunities that will be discussed in the follow-up workshops. The observation will take place three times for each experiment at the following stages and will be based on the following indicators (the indicators will be subjected to an open debate and specialization, though they must be the same for each experiment):

Quantitative:

- Representation of each internal & quadruple helix actor
- Interest in RRI of each internal & quadruple helix actor [at the beginning & end of experiment]
- Awareness of RRI of each internal & quadruple helix actor [at the beginning & end of experiment]
- Perceived usefulness of RRI of each internal & quadruple helix actor [at the beginning & end of experiment]
- Number of RRI best practices evaluated and highly rated by the stakeholders
- Number of internal stakeholders involved in the experiments
- Number of quadruple helix consensus solutions (common agreed plans/steps) for supporting the embedment of RRI
- Number of RRI pillars focused upon
- Number of RRI best practices considered for assessment of their potential implementation in the ongoing research

Qualitative:

- Policy change recommendations
- Organizational change recommendations
- Industry/RFPO proposals for collaboration with researchers
- Society-driven proposals for collaboration with researchers
- Observation of result/best practice multiplication in the quadruple helix ecosystem

Appendix A-F – Indicative structure for the experiment report

Experiment – specific sections (the template will be provided to experiment organizers):

- Executive summary (key points)
- Experiment description
 - Organizer
 - Aim & objectives
 - Selected RRI pillars
- Internal stakeholders' description
- External stakeholders' description
- Focus group outcome summary
- Follow-up interview summary
- Workshop summary

- Lessons learnt
 - Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation
 - Proposed consensus strategies & co-creation approaches/frameworks
 - Most relevant RRI practices (from WP1 and WP2) for the experiment
 - Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars
 - Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix
 - Any issues/constraints noticed during the experiment implementation (i.e. procedural issues)

- Next steps

Comparative report – specific sections (only for SEERC):

- Executive summary
- Experiment 1 report
- Experiment 2 report
- Experiment 3 report
- Experiment 4 report
- Integrated roadmap for quadruple helix co-creation for RRI embedment
 - Specific instructions for each RRI pillar and for each experiment sector
- Policy recommendations
 - Specific recommendations for each RRI pillar and for each experiment sector
- Next steps

Appendix A-G – Scientific background & insights into the methodology development

Introduction

In the context of the First Mutual Learning Workshop, held in Trondheim on November 10th 2017, the need for collecting suggestions about how to organise the experiments was expressed.

On the basis of the literature review carried out under WP1, in this short note some suggestions are given, which mainly refer to the process leading to the design of the experimentations.

As it has been proposed in the Experiment Organization Methodology document, such a process includes a reflexive step, a mapping and consultation step, and a designing step. This note mainly concerns how to develop the first two steps.

The note is organised in four sections:

- Hints for an interpretation of RRI
- Four suggested actions in order to drive the process up to the design of experimentations
- A model of actor in order to facilitate the implementation of the actions
- A set of questions which can be considered as useful for driving the process.

1. An interpretation of RRI

The Literature Review helps provide some hints about how to interpret RRI which can be usefully applied in the context of WP3. In particular, four points can be highlighted.

- A. **RRI concerns R&I as a whole.** RRI does not only concern the relations of researchers and R&I institutions with external stakeholders, but also the internal mechanisms of science, including, e.g., scientific competition, publishing issues, labour relations, peer reviewing and research assessment, organisational issues and the like. Also this aspects actually relates to changing relations between science and society.
- B. **RRI is a set of resources and opportunities.** In this perspective, RRI cannot be understood as a policy framework adding “something new” to the ordinary R&I activities but a policy framework helping researchers and R&I organisations address the issues they are ordinarily involved with and often worried of. In other words, the logic underlying RRI should be not incremental, but transformational. Thus, RRI can be considered as a set of opportunities and resources for researchers and R&I organisations for better doing what they already do.
- C. **RRI is a context-sensitive approach.** The major consequence of the previous assumption is that RRI should be moulded on R&I organisation or group which applies it.
- D. **R&I organisations should be aware of themselves.** The second consequence is that organisations or groups should be aware of themselves, i.e., who are they, how they work, which are the problems they are dealing with and so forth.

2. Suggested actions

These hints can be also put at the basis of the four experiments to be carried out under FIT4RRI WP3.

In order to set up the experiments, **four main actions** can be identified, distributed in the three steps proposed in the Experiment Organization Methodology document.

Reflexive step

- **ESTABLISHING THE ACTOR.** The first action is to establish the “actor”, i.e., the group which is involved in the experiment. To do that, it is necessary to start by operationally identifying the actor in, so to speak, institutionally terms (for example, a research group, a university department, a university institution, a firm, a research group in the firm, a civic association, etc.), and attempting to make an analysis of it.
- **IDENTIFYING THE CRITICAL ISSUES.** The second action is to identify the critical issues the implementing actor is facing, should face or is interested in facing in the next future. This may include both the general trends affecting R&I in general (a list of trends is Appendix H) or local problems (for example, access to resources, interactions with other groups or departments, lack of skills, lack of time, etc.).

Consultation step

- **DEVELOPING A SELF-TAILORED PROFILE OF RRI.** The third action is to develop a self-tailored profile of RRI, i.e., an idea or vision of RRI which can be applicable to the nature and

features of the actor and which can help solve the problems the actor is facing. The key here is to understand the added value of RRI for the actor both to address present or future problems and to open up new opportunities. This process cannot be done only by the group but through a consultation process also involving internal and external stakeholders. At this stage, the option of not engaging the organisation in RRI-oriented actions is also seriously to be considered.

Designing step

- **DESIGNING THE ACTION PLAN.** The fourth action is to **design an action plan**, identifying problems and issues, RRI-oriented actions and their expected outputs pertaining to the four components, so as to make RRI something useful and feasible.

Needless to say, the complexity of such a scheme is quite variable, depending on the size, nature and organisational structure of the actor.

3. A model of actor

In order to facilitate the process shortly described above, a model of collective actor has been proposed in Trondheim.

In the actor, it is possible to distinguish a “**core group**” (sharing the same objectives, passions and action patterns) and an **extended group** (made up of people which support the core group on a regular or an occasional basis).

The main character of the **core group** is that of sharing, largely at an informal level, four main components, i.e.

- Culture
- Agency
- Action
- Identity.

Culture

Culture concerns any cognitive and cultural element providing the set of shared meanings necessary for the group to exist as a group. For example, the culture of a research unit may include its research mission and objectives, the disciplinary culture(s) of the members, the governance styles, the attitudes towards novelties, the symbols and rituals shared by all the members, and the like.

From the RRI-implementation perspective, culture concerns the level of **awareness** the organisation and its members have about what is at stake in RRI.

Agency

Agency concerns the actor’s orientation to act and the energy (in any sense, from money or time to emotional energy) the actor is interested in investing. For example, a research group may be interested in investing in a given kind of research, in cooperating with the private sector, in increasing its visibility in the university, in constantly enlarging the group, in getting engaged with science communication, or in other things.

All in all, the concept of agency refers to the quantity and quality of energy the actor accumulates and is interested in investing and on what. Even though we are speaking of a collective actor, it is quite evident that a pivotal role is played by an individuals' interests, emotions and actual mobilisation.

From the RRI-implementation perspective, agency concerns the way in which RRI becomes **relevant**, i.e., something the organisation and its members recognise as useful for them to address the problems they are facing and worried about.

Action

Action concerns what the actor actually does, how it is to be done, and what effects are produced. While agency represents the cognitive side of the action, the latter represents the actualisation of the former, even though the overlaps between the two may also be limited because of the many contingencies and constraints of the real world.

From the RRI-implementation perspective, the action component concerns the way in which RRI becomes **effective**, i.e., actually useful for the development of the organisation.

Identity

Identity concerns the way in which actors control their own internal and external environment. Identity, therefore, includes any action aimed at ensuring this control and, especially, the interaction systems and networks, as well as all the practices enabling the organisation to coordinate internally and externally.

From the RRI-implementation perspective, identity concerns the way in which RRI becomes part of the daily practices of the organisation, thus becoming **sustainable** in the long run.

A summary scheme

The four components can be viewed as part of a **cycle**, by virtue of which changes in culture (awareness) are expected to modify actor agency (relevance) and, consequently, to produce changes in the actions performed (effectiveness), up to the modification of the internal and external configuration of the organisation (sustainability). However, the cycle can be considered as starting from any component of the model

These dynamics can be schematised as follows.

As a matter of fact, all these components play a pivotal role in these dynamics. In fact:

- Agency mobilisation not based on a RRI culture is **unproductive**, since it leaves mobilised agents isolated within the organisation and without any support
- Agency mobilisation which does not turn into action is **fruitless**
- RRI actions without agency mobilisation reflect a **top-down** and **unrealistic** approach
- RRI actions which do not result in permanent or long-term change in an organization, thus becoming part of the identity of the organization, can be useful in many respects but **useless** for embedding RRI in the ordinary activities of research institutions.
- An identity which does not change the culture of the organisation is **destined to fail**.

4. Issues to drive the process

In this section, a set of issues are proposed, useful for “driving the process” as it was described above, i.e., organised in four main steps (establishing the actor, identifying the critical issues, developing a self-tailored profile of RRI, and designing the experiment).

STRAND 1 - ESTABLISHING THE ACTOR	
Culture	
–	Is the group identifiable with specific institutional boundaries? Which is the “right” group of people in order to implement the experiment?
–	Can the group be identifiable through a specific “mission” or long-term objectives? How can it be described?
–	Can the group be identifiable through specific research approaches and interests, epistemic or theoretical orientations, its belonging to specific a research school or other aspects?
–	Can the group be distinguished from other similar groups through a set of attitudes, cultural orientations, interests, working styles, or internal cooperation styles?
–	Is the group autonomous enough to be actually recognised as a group?
–	Has the group a distinguishable history? Is it shared or known by its present members?
–	Other issues
Agency	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which are the research issues the group is presently involved in? Is it possible to distinguish different sub-groups on the basis of the research issues? - Is the group or some part of it pursuing some institutional or organisational objectives (for example, becoming larger, becoming more autonomous, acquiring new equipment, enlarging the cooperation networks, getting more funds, improving the quality of teaching, etc.)? - Other issues
Action
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it possible to map the main activities and tasks the group is usually involved in (research and lab work, publishing, teaching, administrative work, conference and networking, applying for funds, etc.)? - Is it possible to rank these activities and tasks on the basis of their relative importance and in terms of the time they overall require? - Other issues.
Identity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How the group members coordinate their activities? Who are involved in the coordination activities (e.g., technicians, researchers, teaching staff, students, administrative staff, etc.)? Are there norms, procedures, or regulations guiding the internal life of the group? - How the group interacts with superior and other units within the organisation (e.g., other groups, the department, the faculty, the organisation as a whole, HR department, etc.)? Is it possible to map the contents of these interactions? Are there norms, procedures, or regulations guiding the interaction between the group and these units? - Is it possible to map the actors external to the organisation the group structurally cooperate with (e.g., suppliers, firms, developers, other research groups, scientific societies, local authorities, civil society organisations, etc.)? How can be this relations described? - Other issues

STRAND 2 - IDENTIFYING THE CRITICAL ISSUES
Culture
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping the main critical issues related to the culture of the group, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of cohesion and presence of conflicts • Diverging views about mission, objectives, or the internal life of the group • Disciplinary or scientific divergences • Difficulties in integrating younger staff members in the group's culture and life (e.g., PhD students and post-docs) • Difficulties in preserving the autonomy of the group • Problems related to gender inequality and diversity • Other issues
Agency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping the main critical issues the group members are presently worried about (see also Appendix H) such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The competition in the group's research field(s) • The competition among group's members • The accelerated pace of the research process • The diversification of tasks within the group • Difficulties in retaining young researchers • Difficulties in preserving the autonomy of the group • Difficulties in managing the need for an increased staffing in a context of increasing costs • Over-exploitation and over-training of young researchers • Difficulties related to the increased mobility of researchers • Problems in ensuring high quality research products • Difficulties in accessing research funds • Problems related with peer reviewing and research quality assessment • Problems related with the adoption of entrepreneurial models of research governance • Diverging scientific and personal interests within the group • Other issues
Action

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mapping the main critical issues related to the activities carried out by the group, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of internal coordination and planning • Lack of managerial expertise and soft skills • Problems in managing the diversification of and the increase in activities not related to research work (administrative work, relations with external actors, science communication, innovation-related activities, teaching, etc.) • Excessive administrative constraints and burden • Inadequate resources, staff, funds and equipment • Lack of time • Other issues
Identity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mapping the main critical issues related to the identity of the group, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constraints in the interaction with other internal units and players (e.g., other groups, the department, the faculty, the organisation as a whole, HR department, etc.) • Constraints in the interaction with external players (researchers, research organisations, local authorities, suppliers, firms, developers, interest groups, civil society organisations, etc.) • Lack of effective regulations, norms and procedures • Other issues

STRAND 3 - DEVELOPING A SELF-TAILORED PROFILE OF RRI
Culture
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How RRI could positively impact on the culture of the group and group members – Which of the problems identified under Strand 2 may be better addressed through RRI – Which RRI keys may be considered more appropriate (gender issues, public engagement, education, ethical issues, open access) and which of them is already incorporated in the group’s culture and how – Which RRI dimensions can be considered more appropriate (anticipation, inclusion, responsiveness, reflexivity, etc. –
Agency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How RRI could positively impact on the agency of the group and group members – Which of the problems identified under Strand 2 may be better addressed through RRI – Which RRI keys may be considered more relevant (gender issues, public engagement, education, ethical issues, open access) and which of them is already incorporated in the group’s agency and motivations – Which RRI dimensions can be considered more relevant (anticipation, inclusion, responsiveness, reflexivity, etc.
Action
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How RRI could positively impact on the action of the group and group members – Mapping all the RRI-oriented activities (also not labelled as such) incorporated in the action of the group – Which of the problems identified under Strand 2 may be better addressed through RRI – Which RRI keys may be considered more effective (gender issues, public engagement, education, ethical issues, open access) – Which RRI dimensions can be considered more effective (anticipation, inclusion, responsiveness, reflexivity, etc.
Identity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How RRI could positively impact on the ordinary functioning and structure of the group – Mapping all the RRI-oriented activities (also not labelled as such) incorporated in the ordinary functioning and structure of the group and the organisation the group is part of – Which of the problems identified under Strand 2 may be better addressed through RRI – Which RRI keys may be considered more sustainable (gender issues, public engagement, education, ethical issues, open access) – Which RRI dimensions can be considered more sustainable (anticipation, inclusion, responsiveness, reflexivity, etc.)

DESIGNING THE EXPERIMENT
Culture

– Defining a set of actions for incorporating RRI in the group’s culture, identifying objectives, relations with the main problems the group is addressing, connection with internal and external stakeholders, actions and expected benefits
Agency
– Defining a set of actions for incorporating RRI in the group’s agency, identifying objectives, relations with the main problems the group is addressing, connection with internal and external stakeholders, actions and expected benefits
Action
– Defining a set of actions for incorporating RRI in the group’s activities, identifying objectives, relations with the main problems the group is addressing, connection with internal and external stakeholders, actions and expected benefits
Identity
– Defining a set of actions for incorporating RRI in the group’s identity, identifying objectives, relations with the main problems the group is addressing, connection with internal and external stakeholders, actions and expected benefits

Appendix A-H – Main trends in scientific research

(From the Literature Review WP1)

Trends	Description
1. Hypercompetition	Science as a hypercompetitive environment where the traditional process cycle has collapsed due to time constraints and equilibrium is impossible to sustain
2. Acceleration of the research process	Working faster seen as a requirement for high quality research; changes in the organisation of academic life and in the researchers’ lifestyle; researchers under condition of stress and pressure
3. Shrinking of research funds	Scientists and research organisation working in an increasingly competitive environment, especially in accessing to funds and publishing; decline in the success rate for grant applicants, with an increasing waste of time
4. Task diversification	Market-oriented organisation of the research process, in which research is required to engage with a wider range of different types of activities (participation in extended research networks, direct involvement in innovation and technology transfer, activities related to accountability, transparency and public scrutiny, administrative work, etc.). This is leading to a decrease in the time devoted to scientific work.
5. Increased staffing	Increased numbers of contingent staff (PhD students and Postdocs), due to the need for cost containment; increased use of soft money to pay the contingent staff: fewer opportunities for young researchers to access permanent positions; increased pressure on young researchers to make more in less time, creating hardships especially for women scientists.
6. Increased segmentation	Segmentation of staff based on age and contractual status, producing impacts such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in productivity among young researchers - Increased control over academic tasks - Overtraining (tendency to retain PhD students and Postdocs longer than necessary) - Decrease in teaching quality (increasingly done by ever cheaper teaching staff)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in internal labour relationships (research organisations no longer as a “community of peers” but merely as employers) - Individualisation (researchers increasingly acting as individual professionals and not as part of a staff) - Attitude of self-promotion among scientists - Stratification and polarisation of academic staff (academic staff split between those benefit from change and those who are damaged by it)
7. Increasing mobility	Mobility as a factor promoting an increase in scientific performance but having possible critical impacts on the lives of researchers, such as: delays in accessing permanent positions; difficulties in returning to one’s home country; problems in managing family life, especially for women scientists; loss of social ties
8. increasing pressure on research assessment systems	Traditional research assessment procedures are no longer able to manage the hyperproduction of scientific knowledge; systematic problems and errors in peer review, lessening its reliability; problematic tendency to use quantitative indicators to assess researchers, research institutions and scientific journals, with distorting effects on science quality
9. Governance shift	Tendency to adopt entrepreneurial models for managing research organisations, requiring a balance of different steering mechanisms; high variability in types of research organisations; differentiation in terms of national contexts; strong resistance to change; need for highly participatory approaches.
10. Increasing openness to external actors	Rising complexity in managing research organisations due to growing need to interact with external actors (political authorities, civil society, industry, etc.) for different reasons (innovation, providing expertise, public engagement, policy issues, societal engagement, science communication, etc.); need to find the right openness level; institutional undervaluation of openness-related initiatives; conceptual ambiguities and interpretive mismatches about openness; resistance and barriers to openness; decreasing trust in science
11. Critical dynamics affecting the quality of research products	Impact of changes on the quality of research, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tendency of researchers to adopt safe and low-risk research strategies (favouring conservative and short-term thinking and penalising more creative and unorthodox approaches) - Tendency to produce irrelevant science (producing publications for career advancement rather than producing advances in science) - Tendency to produce redundant papers (publishing the same data or papers more than once) - Tendency to work on research project that ensure short-term achievements and profitable results - Increasing malpractice - Decreasing reproducibility of scientific data - Undesirable impacts of commercial interests on research quality

Appendix A-I – RRI Dimensions

(From Gwizdala, J. P., & Sledzik, K. (2017). Responsible Research and Innovation in the Context of University Technology Transfer. *Folia Oeconomica*, 2.)

Dimension	Description	Authors/Research
Inclusion	<p>Inclusion is a conceptual dimension which can be considered as fundamental for most of the discussions within the RRI area. Inclusion is also associated with all other conceptual dimensions, it engages different stakeholders in the early stages of research and innovation process. When it comes to the discussion of technology transfer and technological issues, it is important not to forget about societal, economic, political and human aspects. Engaging the public stakeholders in early stages of R&D is supposed to positively influence technological development. The example of inclusion in the view of RRI is the Code of Conduct (CoC), which leads various actors to follow the principles of a safe, ethical and effective framework. Many followers of RRI concept see inclusion as the “ongoing involvement of society” in various stages of the research and innovation process, without wasting taxpayers’ money or time at the same time. Inclusion is the conceptual dimension that characterizes RRI the most.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barben, Fisher, Celin & Guston, 2008 - Owen, Macnaghten & Stilgoe, 2012 - Mejlgaard, Bloch, Degn, Nielsen & Ravn, 2012 - Stahl, 2013 - Kearnes, 2013 - Asante, Owen & Williamson, 2014 - Levidow & Neubauer, 2014 - Stahl, McBride, Wakunu-ma & Flick, 2014 - de Saille, 2015 - Bozeman, Rimes & You-tie, 2015 - Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Anticipation	<p>Anticipation is a dimension that aims at envisioning the future of research and innovation. It takes into account understanding how current dynamics help design the future. In research, RRI is also linked to “Real-Time Technology Assessment” or “anticipatory governance”. Anticipatory governance includes the technologies which provide value added advantage and, at the same time, avoid the emergence of potentially negative consequences. Successful anticipation means understanding the dynamics of economy that help shape technological futures. Anticipation of potential impacts of technology serves the purpose of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – reflecting on the motivations and implications of a research project, – being clearer about uncertainties and dilemmas, – opening visions to a broader public, – using the outcomes to shape the research and innovation trajectory. <p>Anticipation plays an important initial role in research and development, indicating the direction to take to achieve better and more desirable results.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Robinson, 2009 - Stirling, 2010 - Selin, 2011 - Roco, Harthorn, Guston & Shapira, 2011 - van den Hove, McGlade, Mottet & Depledge, 2012 - Owen, Macnaghten & Stilgoe, 2012 - Stilgoe, Owen & Macnaghten, 2013 - Stahl, 2013 - Stahl, McBride, Wakunu-ma & Flick, 2014 - Rose (2014) - Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Responsiveness	<p>Responsiveness is linked to risk, which is the probability of an occurrence of an event multiplied by the cost of that event, which new technologies may bring about. The risks involved in new technologies can be medium or long term, economic, environmental, security or societal. In this case, identification and analysis of risks as part of responsiveness is linked to the anticipation dimension. In research, discussions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pellizzoni, 2004 - Owen, Macnaghten & Stilgoe, 2012 - Stilgoe, Owen & Macnaghten, 2013 - Torgersen & Schmidt, 2013 - Schaper-Rinkel, 2013 - Levidow & Neubauer, 2014 - Maynard, 2015

	involving responsiveness are also primarily linked to ethics, risks, transparency and accessibility.	- Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Reflexivity	Reflexivity is linked to public dialogue, science and public collaboration, and anticipation. It can be defined as “holding a mirror up to one’s activities, commitments and assumptions, being aware of the limits of knowledge and being mindful that a particular framing of an issue may not be universally held”. Responsibility turns reflexivity into a public matter. Involving the public in the research may help researchers reflect on the ethical and social dimensions of their work. Science and public collaboration is a key component of reflexivity. By linking reflexivity and anticipation we can avoid the risk of making wrong predictions, especially in the early stages of technological development.	- Wynne, 1993 - Fisher & Mahajan, 2006 - van der Burg, 2009 - Schuurbijs (2011) - Stilgoe, Owen & Macnaghten, 2013 - Forsberg, Quaglio, O’Kane, Karapiperis, van Woensel & Arnaldi, 2015 - Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Sustainability	Although sustainability issues can be found in most research work, it is not clearly referred to as a dimension. In recent research, sustainability is identified as a key driver of innovation, research and development. Sustainability is already starting to affect the competitiveness concept, which will force organizations and business to change their strategy. Research focused on science, technology and innovation for sustainable development is also conducted in the economic field. Sustainability often refers to the so-called resource-efficiency of new products. Research and innovation are closely connected to social responsibility, because they can implement more sustainable innovations (products) in economy. In general, therefore, it can be concluded that sustainability as a conceptual dimension may form part of Responsible Research and Innovation.	- Wright, Gellert, Gutwirth & Friedewald, 2011 - Flipse, van der Sanden & Osse-weijer, 2013 - de Martino, Errichiello, Marasco & Morvillo, 2013 - Stahl, McBride, Wakunu-ma & Flick, 2014 - Levidow & Neubauer, 2014 - Bozeman, Rimes & You-tie, 2015 - Bremer, Millar, Wright & Kaiser, 2015 - Forsberg, Quaglio, O’Kane, Karapiperis, van Woensel & Arnaldi, 2015 - Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Care	The main challenge of future-oriented ethics is to answer the question of how to deal with uncertainties derived from social practices like technology and innovation. Care is a “public domain” dimension so that society is responsible for the decisions and actions carried out on its behalf. Care is also explained as a process through which people develop abilities to perceive, act and judge together. What is important, as regards care as a conceptual dimension of RRI, is the fact that it is crucial not to see inclusion just as a means to meet the “grand challenges” but as a way of bringing together people’s high objectives and day-to-day practices.	- Groves, 2009 - Stilgoe, Owen & Macnaghten, 2013 - Burget, Bardone & Pe-daste, 2016
Economic	Concerns about the impact of new technologies on economy and society explain growing calls for the responsible innovation concept, the sustainable transition of social and technical arrangements, and stronger engagement between science-driven innovation and society. Such issues as those related to RRI are better understood as “aspirations” which may never be fully achieved, suggesting they could only be instantiated through the observation of the practice of science-driven innovation. Innovations are not created only for the creation process. Innovations are implemented in the economy and comply with the requirements of	- Schumpeter, 1934 - Rogers, 1962 - Nelson & Winter, 2002 - Geels, 2010 - Owen & Goldberg, 2010 - Garud & Gehman, 2012 - Armstrong, Cornut, Delacôte & Lenglet, 2012 - Owen, Bessant & Heinz, 2013 - Pandza & Ellwood, 2013 - de Saille, 2015

	meeting needs in terms of value creation for the company, the public and other stakeholders in the process of economic development.	
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Appendix B – Experiment KPIs

The following tables provide a comparative overview for each experiment with regards with each experiment monitoring KPI.

CODE &INDICATOR	EXPERIMENTS			
Scope of the experimentation	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics – Optical Monitoring (Univeristy of Liverpool)	Buildig ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
R1 RRI pillars focused upon*	3	3	2	5
R2 RRI best practices considered for assessment of their potential implementation in the ongoing research*	The participatory process for pointing out issues and indicators for responsible governance (through ToC and BSC) is for sure a best practice. Also, the engagement and education activities will be further implemented.	Strong integration with WP1, WP2 practices as shown in the report.	The best practices are: Openness; Multi-actor process; Improve the quality of research and innovation process; Increase networking opportunities; Increase contribution from all stakeholders; Align science and innovation with societal needs.	20 (All presented in the Benchmarking report)
R3 Connection with existing policies/measures developed by the organisation	The working group and the call for funding on third mission represent a connection with existing measures	Connection with the library licensing of the text and data mining policies.	Ethics policy, public engagement policy, impact case studies, social impact policy, business engagement, consultancy scheme, EU investment	N/A
Agreement				
R4 Degree of agreement of the beneficiaries about the aims of the experiment	N/A	5 (very important for everyone). Interest received. Especially from the working group members – including Elsevier, Crossref, Taylor & Francis – they wanted access to the white paper. Decided not to bring Crossref onboard to avoid competition with the other members.	Interviews with the beneficiaries Ethics – high agreement in university – 5 Science education Care providers – 2 End users – 4 (not so much about ethics but about monitoring)	4/5

R5	Degree of agreement of other concerned actors in the organisation about the aims of the experiment	N/A	5 (very important for everyone).	University – 5 9 of them scored - 5 4 scored - 3 (Internal and external)	4/5
R6	Degree of agreement of quadruple helix actors about the aims of the experiment	N/A	Civil society was not involved. All other actors fully agree (5). End of the experiment is beneficial indeed for the society.	Liverpool city council – agreement 5 9 of them scored - 5 4 scored - 3 (Internal and external)	4/5
Mobilisation of internal actors					
R7	Active involvement of the organisation's management *	The experiment was implemented by the research and TT area of Sapienza, that represent one of university management office. Furthermore, the governing bodies have always been informed	No meeting yet – however to a certain level yes. Since the project is quite external and based on a very decentralized business model the role of the higher management is not so important.	Ethics committee structure- senior management, PRO VCs, heads of departments, members of ethcis committes, Council, ethics committee in December (no ad hoc meetings)	The director of the R&D Department is personally involved, as well as the heads of the units. The administration is aware and following the implementation of the experiment.
R8	Active involvement of researchers *	Researchers both from Saperi&Co. and of Department of Chemical, Material and Environmental Engineering jopined meetings regularly and were involved both in the design and implementation of the experiment. Researchers from other areas also joined the workshops.	Good involvement: 3 internal researchers. Further engagement was done through working groups.	Yes – the primary ones + extended - + Industry 4.0 researchers + PhD students are involved in the project.	All ISQ researchers (46+ internships) have been involved at least at one of the workshops promoted by the experiment.
Mobilisation of external actors					
R9	Active involvement of quadruple helix actors*	Quadruple helix actors were highly involved in all activities (especially workshops) concerning the governance pillar	The actors were involved (besides society).	Full engagement	N/A

**CODE &
INDICATOR**

EXPERIMENTS

Implementation process	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics – Optical Monitoring (Univeristy of Liverpool)	Buildig ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
E1 Actual implementation of the planned actions	The experiment was implemented according to the plans. With more time available, even thje guidelines could have been defined	Everything is set – no major delay. (Small delay with the first meeting. Afterwards it was mitigated. Delays in composing the shite paper. Four meetings in total – against the 2 planned ones)	On time	15/19 steps of the original plan have been implemented
E2 Compliance with planned schedules and deadlines	See E1	So far on track. (OK)	On time	Medium
Beneficiaries				
E3 Match between the number of beneficiaries planned/ number of actual beneficiaries	N/A	Good match (4). Good interest in the beginning however throughout the meetings some people lost interest. Still 4-5 actors stayed onboard.	Full match.	Don't know exactly how to report; all ISQ researchers are beneficiaries of the experiment, which doesn't mean that they all participated in all activities carried out during the experiment
E4 Match between the type of intended beneficiaries and the type of the actual beneficiaries	There was a good matching	The only category that was not included is civil society (beneficiary). However, they will receive all the outputs through the dissemination channels.	Full match.	We missed a greater involvement of external stakeholders who were a little left behind in the course of the experiment

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EXPERIMENTS

Objective impact – Institutional agreement	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics – Optical Monitoring (Univeristy of Liverpool)	Buildig ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
I1 Number of quadruple helix consensus solutions (common agreed plans/steps) for supporting the embedment of RRI *	Sapienza has activated a formal agreement with AIRI	The RRI experiment was somewhat different and it focused mostly on educating the stakeholders. There was not major disagreement among the stakeholders.	2 - Going out to the community and speaking with people- was agreed in the focus groups More emphasis on trainings and the means of training (better quality trainings)	N/A
Objective impact – Expected changes				
I2 Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes at the level of the research group/department/quadruple helix actors directly involved with the experiment	Surely the engineering researchers involved in the experiment are much more aware of RRI and its benefits	No specific change. More training actions/seminars introduced. Good internal learning exercise.	Internal exercises for the PGR school Revision of the ethics strategy	New training programme on RRI for any new researcher recruited to ISQ's R&D Department
I3 Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in parts of the organisation not directly involved with the experiment	The call for funding will be open to the entire Sapienza community	No specific change was introduced.	After the workshop internal participant agree to embed RRI participants into their roles within their current positions.	Gender balance annual reporting specifically regarding ISQ's R&D Department
I4 Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in external organisations (quadruple helix actors)	N/A	No specific change was introduced (besides the learning path).	In the evaluations from the workshop external participants stated they would use RRI principals moving forward within their organisations.	N/A
Objective impact – Unexpected effects				
I5 Occurrence of unexpected effects concerning the involved actors (e.g. unplanned introduction of new norms, policies, or procedures; establishment of new networks or groups as	N/A	New collaborations emerged with the stakeholders.	We will have a follow up on this matter. No unexpected effects up to date.	Creation of a new R&D Department

	an effect of the experiment; etc.)				
Objective impact – Multiplicative effects					
I6	Observation of result/best practice multiplication in the quadruple helix ecosystem generated through the experiment *	As already mentioned, there is a growing attention in Sapienza towards responsibility and sustainability actions. These go beyond the experiment but have been partly influenced by it.	Ethics best practices; researchers became interested to multiply/replicate the findings. Crossref (external stakeholder) might have been interested. Good interest from the learning perspective – some issues related to whom will lead this.	No results as yet, however further dissemination may provide some observational effects beyond the scope of the experiment.	RRI dimension included in new projects and project designs
Objective impact – Communication impacts					
I7	Increased visibility of the experiment within the organisation	The engagement and education activities of the experiment have been well promoted on Sapienza website and newsletter as well as on social channels (e.g. twitter)	Not so much – due to decentralization and the lack of interference among the teams.	Yes – internal communication, departments, RRI training in PGR studies Focus groups with SMEs	Medium
I8	Increased visibility of the experiment outside the organisation	See I7	Yes, due to publications & events.	Focus groups with SMEs	Medium-high
Subjective impact – Degree of agreement with the experimentation					
I9	Degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries about the activities carried out	N/A	High interest/satisfaction from the interest group members.	Very high satisfaction (4/5).	5/5
I10	Degree of satisfaction of the Teams about the activities carried out	N/A	The team is satisfied.	Good level of satisfaction (3.5/5)	High
I11	Degree of satisfaction of the actors internal to the organisation about the activities carried out	N/A	Good (4)– but not so often involved.	Good levels of satisfaction (see the report).	5/5
I12	Degree of satisfaction of the quadruple helix actors about the activities carried out	N/A	Very satisfied (5).	Good levels of satisfaction (see the report).	N/A

I13	Number of RRI best practices evaluated and highly rated by the stakeholders *	N/A	Mostly interested in learning about RRI as a whole.	(4) - Inclusion, Open Access, Ethics of research RRI Toolkit from the FOSTER Platform	7: RRI-oriented platform and networking; RRI-oriented code of conduct; “Top-down” approach; RRI-oriented comprehensive training; Business-oriented approach to RRI; STEM and social sciences institutional partnerships; Local networks.
Subjective impact – Changes in the perception of RRI/OS					
I14	Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	All these dimensions (I14 to I21) will be assessed once the guidelines will be developed through a dedicated survey	In the beginning they didn’t know about RRI/OS and then they became interested (towards the end of the experiment).	This has been included in the report	3/5 Positive change in most of the cases – very much in line with the taylor-made approach used in the experiment
I15	Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *		In the beginning they didn’t know about RRI/OS and then they became interested (towards the end of the experiment).	This has been included in the report	N/A
I16	Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *		Yes – became more aware (4).	This has been included in the report	4/5
I17	Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *		Yes – became more aware (4).	This has been included in the report	N/A

I18	Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *		It is more about the usefulness of the learning component (4).	Included in the report	4/5
I19	Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *		It is more about the usefulness of the learning component (4).	Included in the report	N/A
Subjective impact – Orientation towards future involvement					
I20	Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of each internal actors		Since they were not so much involved – therefore this experiment might not have created a momentum.	Mostly yes (12 out of 13)	High (4/5)
I21	Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of quadruple helix actors		Similar to the above – since the end product is promoted as a technology – not so much as RRI.	Mostly yes (12 out of 13)	N/A

CODE & INDICATOR

EXPERIMENTS

Recommendations produced	Material Science (Sapienza)	Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data (Open University)	Photonics – Optical Monitoring (Univeristy of Liverpool)	Buildig ISQ RRI Model (ISQ)
S1 Policy change recommendations *	The experiment for sure offers a solid base for future RRI oriented policies	Nothing observed/ mentioned due to the decentralized approach of Open University.	Ethics and PGR (internal)	Yes,; RRI Training + others (defining a new R&D department based on RRI).
S2 Organisational change recommendations *	Similarly, the experiment has launched possible RRI oriented organizational practices	Nothing observed/ mentioned due to the decentralized approach of Open University.	Ethics board.	Restructuring the R&D department An ISQ-RRI model to be included in the policy of the organize.
Institutional links and agreements				

S3	Creation of links with key players not previously engaged in the implementation of the experiment		To some extent yes (i.e. Crossref, Elsevier) – through the networks of Taylor & Francis, Jisc.	Link with the research support department and a community engagement event.	Externals tangenot to the new R&D department.
S4	Creation of stable links with other bodies involved in the implementation of the experiment	For sure the stakeholders involved in the experiment have expressed their wish to keep working more permanently on the theme. AIRI has already organized a technical table for RRI in industry using the experiment as a successful use case	To some extent (depends on future funding).	Link with the research support department and a community engagement event.	Yest with SEERC, CV, Minho and future RRI projects (already capitalized in new funded projects).
S5	Industry/RFPO proposals for collaboration with researchers *	New programs seem possible	Potentially yes. Clear strategy for this.	Yes (interest has been received for joint proposals).	Yes – engagement in new fundd EU projects on RRI.
S6	Society-driven proposals for collaboration with researchers *	New programs seem possible	Nothing since society was not fully embedded.	Possibility of more after community event has been held	N/A/
<i>Institutionalisation processes within the organisation</i>					
S7	Identification/acquisition of new resources to continue the activities or parts of them	Among the resources there are for sure new call for proposal under H2020 but also cooperation with ongoing projects such as CIVIS or EuSRExcel	Not yet. Involvement in new proposals.	Not yet	Internal support & financing. EU funded projects (i.e. REACT).
S8	Establishment of institutional arrangements to make the new operational setups activated by the actions definitive (e.g., institutionalisation of scholarships, drafting of internal regulations that establish procedures to access certain benefits, etc).	There are no permanent solutions yet, but some pilot experimentations such as the call for funding	Nothing observed or mentioned.	In the PGR	RRI Training & RRI as a core R&D method in ISQ.